

Apicoectomy: A Surgical Approach to Root Canal Treatment Failure- A Case Report

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Abstract

Endodontic surgery is a safe and adequate alternative when teeth are not responding to conventional treatment and endodontic re-treatment. Endodontic treatment failures can be related to: extra radicular infections such as periapical pathology; to foreign body reactions that can be caused by endodontic material extrusion; to endogenous cholesterol crystal accumulation in apical tissues and unresolved cystic lesion. Endodontic surgery comprehends a set of procedures recommended in periapical diseases treatment. A root end surgery, also known as apicoectomy , apicectomy , retrograde root canal treatment or root-end filling, is an endodontic surgical procedure whereby a tooth's root tip is removed and a root end cavity is prepared and filled with a bio-compatible material. It is an example of a periradicular surgery. The main goal of apical surgery is to prevent bacterial leakage from the root-canal system into the periradicular tissues by placing a tight root-end filling following root-end resection which will allow a favourable environment for periapical healing with good long-term prognosis.

Advantages of a new technique for apicoectomy using dental operating microscope and ultrasonic tips in comparison to the traditional technique. Literature review demonstrates success rate to above 90% when employing dental operating microscope and ultrasonic tips for Apicoectomy procedure.

Key words: Apicoectomy, Apicectomy, Retrograde root canal treatment, Root canal failure, Re-RCT.

Introduction

Surgical endodontics is a reliable method for the treatment of teeth with periapical lesions that do not respond to conventional root canal treatment or when ortho grade treatment is not feasible. Also an immature or mature tooth with an open apex causes the problems of overfilling and poor apical seal. So an apical barrier is extremely needed. Retrograde filling is necessary to fill the apical canal space and to obtain a three dimensional seal between the perio dontium and root canal system. The objectives of surgical approach are to remove diseased tissue, debride the canal system as far as possible and to seal the cavity or defect to prevent or reduce the spread of microorganism in the periradicular tissues, thereby providing an environment conducive of regeneration of a normal periodontal apparatus.¹

Indications for Surgical Endodontics:

1. Radiological findings of apical periodontitis and/or symptoms associated with an obstructed canal.
2. Extruded material with clinical or radiological findings of apical Periodontitis and/or symptoms continuing over a prolonged period.
3. Persisting or emerging disease following root-canal treatment when root canal re-treatment is inappropriate.

4. Perforation of the root or the floor of the pulp chamber and where it is impossible to treat from within the pulp cavity.

5. In addition, traumatic injury, cases with severe destructive processes due to furcation or sub- gingival caries, and large root perforations also require surgical endodontics procedure.²

Contra-Indications for Surgical Endodontics:

1. Strong adjacent teeth available for bridge abutments as alternatives to hemisection
2. Inoperable canals in root to be retained
3. Fused roots making separation impossible
4. The tooth has no function (no antagonist, no strategic importance serving as a pillar for a fixed prothesis)
5. Unrestorable tooth
6. Periodontally compromised tooth and
7. An uncooperative patient or a medically compromised patient for an oral surgical intervention.

The treatment success is qualified by major factors including the correct indication, the correct technique, the follow up and

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patient's observance of the post-surgery recommendations. The treatment outcome of apical surgery needs periodic clinical and radiographic assessment.³

Risks associated with Surgical Endodontics

The major risk of apicoectomy is that it simply does not relieve a patient's symptoms. If the area does not heal or continues to cause pain, this is consistent with apicoectomy failure and is considered a poor outcome. If this occurs, the patient may need a second apicoectomy or the tooth may need to be extracted. If too much bone is removed during apicoectomy, it may prevent the placement of a dental implant in the future. As with any dental surgery, there is a small risk of infection, bleeding, or nerve damage.^{4,5}

Outcomes and Prognosis

When performed by an experienced endodontist on properly selected patients, the apicoectomy success rate is quite high. When researchers collected and analyzed results from 21 clinical trials including over 1,600 patients, they found that 59% of patients treated with traditional root end surgery had a positive outcome six months after the apicoectomy procedure (Setzer, Shah, Kohli, Karabucak, & Kim, 2010). On the other hand, 94% of patients who underwent endodontic microsurgery (EMS) for their apicoectomies had a positive outcome. A positive outcome, in this case, was evidence of healing and the absence of pain, swelling, and sensitivity in the affected tooth. Indeed, patients will know they have had a successful apicoectomy if the procedure relieved their pain and related symptoms.⁶

Case Report

A 25 years old male patient, reported to Chandra Dental College and Hospital with complaint of pain and swelling in tooth #12, & presented a history of endodontic treatment irt #11 & #12 both. On clinical examination the apical area of the tooth was exposed with discharging pus. Radiographic examination revealed periapical radiolucency around root apex along with inadequate endodontic therapy irt #12. Patient reported no significant medical and personal history.

Procedural Steps:

1. Flap design markings
2. Incision given
3. Full thickness mucoperiosteal flap raised
4. Window preparation done
5. Diseased tissue removed
6. Root-end resection
7. Root-end preparation
8. Retrograde filling with MTA
9. Single interrupted suturing done

Fig. 1 Sinus tract present irt #12

Fig.2: Full thickness mucoperio steal flap raised, window preparation & removal of pathology

Fig.3 Root end resection & Preparation

Fig.4 After placement of MTA as root-end filling material

Fig.5 Sutures placed

Fig. 6 Post-operative (Radiograph view)

Fig. 7 3- months follow-up radiograph

Discussion

Apical lesions can occur or recur in dental organs with endodontic treatment when the root canal system has not been properly cleaned, shaped and disinfected by instrumentation and copious irrigation, or the absence of disinfection, or due to apical or coronal leakage. Apicoectomy is the standard surgical procedure for such type of endodontic cases to still preserve the tooth.

Endodontic surgery entails the excision of damaged periapical tissue in order to create the perfect conditions for tissue health, regeneration, and the formation of new tooth structural support. When performed for the first time, endodontic surgery has a success rate of between 78 and 91% but is less successful in retreatment situations where there is a periapical lesion.⁷

Anatomical study of the root apex showed that at least 3 mm of the root-end must be removed to reduce 98% of the apical ramifications and 93% of the lateral canals. The essential shortcomings of the conventional rotary bur type of preparation were addressed in this work using the ultrasonic tip for precise retro cavity preparation.⁸

In this case, MTA was chosen as a retrograde filling material than other due to its properties. Easy and moisture independent application, superior seal, bio-compatibility and ability to increase the vulnerable root strength was the considerable factors. Different studies showed better sealing ability regarding MTA while permitted cemento blast attachment and growth. The production of mineralized matrix gene and protein expression indicated that MTA could be considered cemento conductive.⁹

The advantage of surgical endodontics over non-surgical

endodontics is the ability to address the entire root canal system and complete elimination of bacteria.

This case describes how teeth with extensive periapical lesions and recurrent complaints might be treated successfully with a well-performed periapical surgery using MTA as a root end filling material.

Conclusion

Based on the contemporary understanding of endodontic concepts for success and failure, assessment, and subsequent treatment of apicoectomy procedures have greatly improved. Advancements in apicoectomy armamentaria and materials have enabled endodontists to treat challenging cases with much greater efficacy. The surgical technique, which has been, applied in this case i.e. apicoectomy, was appropriate and the results were satisfactory. Hence, apical surgery is a predictable option to save the tooth that is unmanageable by conventional, non surgical endodontics. Endodontic surgery can be used as a solution in situations where the standard endodontic therapy is inadequate. Materials and surgical-related technologies are continually being improved upon in order to make them easier to use and increase success predictability.

References

- [1] G. Korkhaus, "Recent studies on the disinfection of the devitalized tooth," *SSO Schweiz Monatsschr Zahnheilkd*, vol. 60, pp. 1134–1137, 1950.
- [2] B. P. F. A. Gomes, M. E. Vianna, A. A. Zaia, J. F. A. Almeida, F. J. Souza-Filho, and C. C. R. Ferraz, "Chlorhexidine in endodontics," *Brazilian Dental Journal*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 89–102, 2013.
- [3] A. S. Carvalho, L. D. D. Oliveira, F. G. D. Rosa Cardoso, and F. E. D. Oliveira, "Limewater and polymyxin B associated with NaOCl for endotoxin detoxification in root canal with necrotic pulp," *Brazilian Dental Journal*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 573–577, 2016.
- [4] A. Abu Hasna, D. M. D. T. Ungaro, A. A. P. De Melo et al., "Nonsurgical endodontic management of dens invaginatus: a report of two cases," *F1000Research*, vol. 8, p. 2039, 2019.
- [5] Evans GE, Bishop K, Renton T. Guidelines for Surgical Endodontics. RCS 2012; 1-9.
- [6] Shaheen S, Majumder D, Chowdhury D, Mazumder P, Das UK. Healing Of Periapical Lesion In Maxillary Anterior Region With Mineral Trioxide Aggregate Using Retrograde Technique After Apicoectomy - A Case Report. *IJIR*. 2017; 3(3):1720-1723.
- [7] Locurcio L L, Leeson R. A case of peri-radicular surgery: apicoectomy and obturation of the apex, a bold act. *Stomatological Dis Sci* 2017; 1: 76-80
- [8] Srinivasan M R, Nishanthine C. Endodontic Surgery: Is it an obsolete clinical procedure? *J Oper Dent Endod*. 2017; 2(1): 40-44.
- [9] Carr G B. Ultrasonic root end pre-preparation. *Dent Clin N Am*. 1997; 41: 541-554